

Fundamental Right situation in India through R.T.I Act 2005

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1 Abstract

This research article is the true reflection of the country which is established through a democratic country The India. The constitution is the back bone of the country only and many people struggled to safe guard the constitution through different modes as Judiciary at Supreme Court of India and other bodies which are partially helping the country on the ground of different level and representing at large Public Interest.

1.1 Introduction

The Right of Information act 2005 is established as the the Fundamental Right of the people of India. whereas the face value of RTI act 2005 is different , at different channels in all over the India which is truly investigated by the Author as a real life exposure and investigation at all ground in the time being in force.

1.2 Modes of RTI act 2005 Operation in Public Domain

In many government bodies web-pages in India , RTI is presented in the fainter form through a icon which clearly depicts about the transparency and accountability of the government institution and in all the 24 Hon' ble High Court's websites and Hon' ble Supreme Court of India. still we the people of India are never in a way to get the RTI information within 24 hour under section 7(1) of RTI act 2005. In the books of National Council of Educational Research and Training the Right to equality is mentioned very clearly but in the eyes of law the RTI act 2005 can not have overriding effects in Judiciary of Indian Courts. and In Indian Police services even they are Public Servants to safeguard Public of India at larger public Interest about their sovereignty, integrity, fraternity at all extent, their are different channels, too which works for RTI act 2005.

As mention in section 22 of RTI act 2005 which says very important scope of RTI Act 2005 , which author eager to put attention of the editor/ public at large public interest as mentioned below

U/s 22. Act to have overriding effect.—The provisions of this Act shall have effect notwithstanding anything inconsistent therewith contained in the Official Secrets Act, 1923 (19 of 1923), and any other law for the time being in force or in any instrument having effect by virtue of any law other than this Act.

1.3 Working of State Information Commission in Uttar Pradesh - India.

In the present epoch of time the RTI act 2005 is a very dangerous to some agency which are working against the democratic public and missuses their power awarded through government. Among on top of them is investigation agency in India which are part of scale time factor, even the some of agency are not using the guidelines of original RTI act 2005 as also it has been seen that Hon'ble Allahabad High court had made its own RTI Rules-Regulation and Denomination of 50 rupees are needed in asking only one question in RTI information with the Court. Secondly the Second appeal u/s 19(3) after the completion of First appeal by the first appellate authority is delaying it for longer period of time at RTI Bhawan Lucknow on ground reality, and this is in a way to prevent government members working style accuracy and privacy and this leading to corruption in some agencies as the example is 2G spectrum scandal, The most irritating situation is that RTI Bhawan at Lucknow or state information commission is not accepting any application u/s 18(3) of RTI act 2005. On the Other hand the definition of RTI act is clearly defined by section 2, which says inspection, discovery, samples ,anythings and collection of records with any government and semi government agency for transparency.

1.4 Implementation of RTI 2005 by Allahabad High Court

Although the Hon'ble Allahabad High court view is clear in RTI act 2005. In the very judgement of Allahabad High court it can be seen that the Asia's Biggest Bench Court spectrum is very rigid and appreciating in every respect , In the light of observation some Hon'ble Justice stand with the Public are protecting their fundamental Rights using their inherent power , even the pending of cases in the Hon'ble Allahabad High court is in five figure number but still the court of law work for Justice of the Public of Uttar Pradesh. One of the Judgement in which can be use as Citation is the Judgement of year 2019 , 01 November of Hon'ble J, Sudhir Agarwal with Hon'ble J Rajeev Mishra in WRIT C No. 35213 for section 19(3) of second appeal of RTI act 2005 is as mentioned below.

Hon'ble Sudhir Agarwal,J.
Hon'ble Rajeev Misra,J.

1. Heard Sri Ghanshyam Maurya, Advocate for petitioner with learned Standing Counsel as well as Sri Kunal Ravi Singh, Advocate for respondents.

2. The only grievance raised by petitioner is that he filed appeal (Second Appeal) before State Information Commissioner under Section 19(3) of Right to Information Act, 2005 (hereinafter referred to as "Act, 2005") on 07.06.2019 but the same has not been decided so far.

3. Sri Kunal Ravi Singh, Advocate appearing for Respondent-2 states that appeal has been registered but could not give any reason as to why it has not been decided so far.

4. The purpose of Statute was to provide information to citizens expeditiously and that is why Statute has also provided a time schedule within which the applications submitted by citizens for information should be decided but if authorities keep appeals and applications of citizens pending for months together, we have no hesitation in observing that the very purpose of Statute would stand frustrated and that too in the hands of those authorities who are responsible for execution and implementation of the provisions of Act, 2005 which was enacted for a very pious and important constitutional aspect, i.e., "Right to Information". Such attitude on the part of Information Commissioners, whether at lowest level or highest level, cannot be appreciated and it shows that they are not diligently discharging their duties and frustrating the entire purpose of Statute. Having said so, we dispose of this writ petition directing Respondent-2, i.e., Appellate Authority to decide appeal in question within a period of one month from the date of production of a certified copy of this order.

1.5 Online mode of RTI Act 2005

That on the very use of RTI act 2005 by the central government had served the Public the online platform to seek RTI 2005 information. through online mode of operation in ten rupees of denomination, if the matter is related to state government use section 6(3) Of RTI act 2005.

<https://rtionline.gov.in/>

Hon'ble Supreme Court Of India RTI related matter is associated with other 24 Hon'ble High Courts use section 6(3) of RTI act 2005 so the matter will be transferred to the concerned Hon' ble High Courts in online mode.

registry.sci.gov.in/rti.....app

2 Conclusion

On the very discussion and rigorous investigation it is no doubt that entire public of India is eager to make the country corruption free in every respect and some of the High Courts under Article 227, 228 with 226 is supporting the peoples in large extent.

But the duty of public is not bounded or restricted they must understand that section 8 can not be invoked / used by the Public authorities at largest public interest, the investigation agency using misleading statement to misguide, misconduct which is crime in every respect though giving wrong information to public is violation of fundamental right of the people. According to basic law of Jurisprudence the agency has to be work in the direction of natural law of Justice. On the other hand Author seeking amendment under RTI act 2005 to bind with Prevention of Corruption Act and Prevention of Money Laundering Act which will safe guard the RTI act 2005

3 Results

The finality's of the research article is that always file RTI act 2005 in online mode and send the RTI application through email of Public Information Officer and First appellate Authority send all RTI correspondence on time. Author correspondence can be accepted at email astrophysicsinvestigation@gmail.com For suggestion kindly put your valuable remarks and corrections .

3.1 References :

1. State Of U.P vs Raj Narain Ors on 24 January, 1975
Equivalent citations: 1975 AIR 865, 1975 SCR (3) 333
Bench: Ray, A.N. (Cj), Mathew, Kuttibil Kurien, Alagiriswami, A., Sarkaria, Ranjit Singh, Untwalia, N.L.
2. MATTERS UNDER ARTICLE 227 No. - 6404 of 2022
Hon' ble Justice Piyush Agarwal , Dated 30.08.2022
Hon'ble Allahabad High Court.